

S10: Narratives, affects and mobilizations

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The role of filmmaking in creating narratives around mobility: the case of a filmmaking competition of rural women's transport in Tungurahua, Ecuador

Most of the studies on Transit-Oriented Development (TOD) are related to how people move, rather than the impact of TOD on people and their community life. Moreover, the majority of studies use morphological or statistical lenses with little or no attention to the human experience of mobility. Some authors challenge this trend with methodologies focusing on people and their well-being rather than solely on their choices of transport. Echoing this trend, this paper proposes art as a lens to study TOD, specifically through the art of documentary filmmaking. Some authors have already proposed to include artists in official planning processes; however, this paper goes beyond public policy, and the objective is to explore art and the process of making art as a possible transformational tool for those making and receiving art. A second objective is to question the assumption that “experts” know a situation better than the affected parties. A key question is how narratives change when other types of actors tell the story. This study uses a film contest entitled: “Between the countryside and the city: stories of rural women’s transport”^{*} to see what happens when the production of knowledge is made by “non-experts”. The analysis includes the footage of the two winners of the contest, a webinar, and interviews with the organizations and participants involved.

^{*} This contest was co-created with the house of Ecuadorian culture of Tungurahua, GIZ- Ecuador, Grupo FARO (a local NGO), and Cinecyclo Ecuador. It took place between January and October 2020, in the province of Tungurahua (Ecuador).